

Appendix A

Legend of the anthropo-natural landscape map of the year 2021 (from: Ramón and Bollo, 2023 [25]).

A. Physiographic Province Neovolcanic Transmexican Axis, Mil Cumbres subprovince

I. Volcano-tectonic mountains, denudative-erosive, conical in shape with horseshoe-shaped collapse structures (calderas), (1,800-2,641 masl) in a subhumid temperate climate, ranging from slightly to heavily dissected ($200 < V_d < 500$), with slopes ranging from slightly to heavily inclined (0-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, basalts, acidic extrusive igneous rocks, limolites, and conglomerates, with Andosol, Acrisol, and Luvisol soils, and mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, broadleaf forests, and cloud forests coverages.

1. Volcanic cone and domes, with slopes ranging from flat to very steep (0-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with humic Andosol and chromic Luvisol soils, and primary pine-oak forests, primary pine forests, and secondary forests predominantly of pine-oak herbaceous species.

2. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-20o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia with humic Andosol soil, and coverages of rainfed agriculture, permanent crops, secondary pine-oak forests with herbaceous predominance.

3. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-45o), composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks with humic Andosol and orthic Acrisol soils, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests, secondary pine-oak forests with herbaceous predominance, primary pine forests, and secondary pine-oak forests with shrub predominance.

4. (4_1 - 4_2) Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of basalts, with humic Andosol soil, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests and secondary pine forests.

5. Volcano-erosive depression, with steep slopes (10-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol, humic Andosol, and orthic Acrisol soils, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests and secondary pine-oak forests.

II. Volcano-tectonic mountains, denudative-erosive, with horseshoe-shaped collapse structures (calderas), (1,965-2,608 masl) in a subhumid temperate climate, ranging from slightly to heavily dissected ($200 < V_d < 500$), with slopes ranging from slight to very steep (0-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, basalts, acidic extrusive igneous rocks, limolites, and conglomerates, with Acrisol, Andosol, Luvisol, and Ranker soils, and mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, broadleaf forests, and cloud forests coverages.

6. (6_1 - 6_3) Volcanic cone, with slopes ranging from flat to very steep (0-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with orthic Acrisol, humic Andosol, and Ranker soils, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests, secondary pine-oak forests, primary pine forests.

7. (7_1 - 7_5) Volcanic domes, with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with humic Andosol, orthic Acrisol, and chromic Luvisol soils, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests, secondary pine-oak forests, induced grasslands, primary pine forests.

8. (8_1 - 8_7) Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol and orthic Acrisol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests, induced grasslands, and primary pine-oak forests.

9. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks, with orthic Acrisol soil, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests, secondary pine forests, and primary pine forests.

10. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of conglomerates, with chromic Luvisol and orthic Acrisol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests, induced grasslands, and permanent crops.

11. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of limolite-sandstone, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests and induced grasslands.

12. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of rhyolitic tuffs, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests.

13. (13_1 - 13_7) Volcano-erosive depression, with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with orthic Acrisol, humic Andosol, and chromic Luvisol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests and primary pine-oak forests.

III. Polygenetic volcano-tectonic mountains, denudative-erosive, in a subhumid temperate climate, ranging from slightly to heavily dissected ($200 < VD < 500$), (1,294-2,837 masl) with slopes ranging from slight to heavily inclined (1-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, basalts, acidic extrusive igneous rocks, limolites, and conglomerates, with Luvisol and Regosol soils, and mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, broadleaf forests.

14. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol and dystrophic Regosol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests with herbaceous predominance, induced grasslands, and secondary pine-oak forests with shrub predominance.

15. Foothills with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of limolite-sandstone, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests with herbaceous predominance and induced grasslands.

IV. Denudative volcano-tectonic mountains (1,327-2,302 masl) in a subhumid temperate climate, moderately dissected ($200 < DV < 300$), with slopes ranging from slight to steep (0-30o), composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks and andesite-volcanic breccia, with Acrisol and Andosol soils, and mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, broadleaf forests.

16. (16_1 - 16_23) Summits with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks, with orthic Acrisol soil, and coverages of primary pine-oak forests and secondary pine-oak forests.

17. (17_1 - 17_5) Slopes, with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks, with orthic Acrisol soil, and coverages of primary pine forests, secondary pine forests, and secondary pine forests with herbaceous predominance.

18. (18_1 - 18_4) Fluvio-denudative, erosive, V-shaped valleys, with slopes ranging from slight to steep (5-30o) and intermittent river currents, composed of acidic extrusive igneous rocks, with orthic Acrisol soil, and coverages of primary pine forests and secondary pine forests.

B. Physiographic province Sierra Madre del Sur, subprovince Balsas Depression. **V.** Denudative volcano-erosive mountains (984-2,384 masl), in a subhumid temperate climate, moderately to heavily dissected ($300 < VD < 500$), with moderately to heavily inclined slopes (10-45o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia and conglomerates, with Luvisol, Feozem, Regosol, and Acrisol soils, and mixed coniferous and broadleaf forests, deciduous lowland forests, and broadleaf forests.

19. (19_1 - 19_7) Denudative volcano-mountains with slopes ranging from flat to steep (0-30o), composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol, haplic Feozem, and eutric Regosol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests, induced grasslands, and secondary deciduous lowland forests.

20. Denudative volcano-mountains with slopes ranging from strong to very steep (30-45o), composed of conglomerates, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of induced grasslands and secondary pine-oak forests with shrub predominance.

21. (21_1 - 21_2) Fluvio-denudative-erosive valleys, V-shaped, with slopes ranging from slight to very steep (5-45o), and permanent river currents, composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol, haplic Feozem, and eutric Regosol soils, and coverages of induced grasslands, secondary pine-oak forests, and secondary deciduous lowland forests.

22. (22_1 - 22_59) Fluvio-denudative valleys, erosive, V-shaped, with slopes ranging from slight to very steep (5-45o), and intermittent river currents, composed of andesite-volcanic breccia, with chromic Luvisol, haplic Feozem, and eutric Regosol soils, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests, secondary deciduous lowland forests, and induced grasslands.

23. Fluvio-denudative valleys, erosive, V-shaped, with slopes ranging from slight to very steep (5-45°), and permanent river currents, composed of conglomerates, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of secondary deciduous lowland forests, secondary pine-oak forests, and induced grasslands.

24. Fluvio-denudative valleys, erosive, V-shaped, with slopes ranging from slight to very steep (5-45°), and intermittent river currents, composed of conglomerates, with chromic Luvisol soil, and coverages of secondary pine-oak forests.